

THE IMPORTANCE OF CYBERSPACE TOOLS IN THE TRANSFORMATION OF MORAL AND AESTHETIC NEEDS.

Rajabov Shukhratjon Sheralievich

International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan
associate professor, doctor of philosophy (PhD).
shuxrat_rajabov@bk.ru. Tel: 99893 003-11-33
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ABSTRACT

Today, the transformation of personal needs is taking place in the Internet, media products, video games, social networks, and marketing activities, which are attracting the interest of the general public. The global popularity, the status of current networks, as well as the influence of social networks on our traditional moral and aesthetic values are issues that require special research. Cyberspace tools play a key role in satisfying personal aesthetic needs and changing the aesthetic outlook. Due to the need of people to communicate using the technical capabilities of the Internet, a new field and direction called "Social networks" was formed. The fact that social networks, which initially served only to communicate with someone, are now becoming an incomparable tool for people who respond to the social and political changes taking place in the life of society with their advanced thoughts.

Intraduction. At the current stage of development, the demand for social relations has not decreased. Only now the methods of meeting this demand are changing. Social relations themselves have acquired a new look. We are talking about social networks known to all of us. In a short time, social networks have become extremely popular in the virtual world. In this respect, they can be called a truly new phenomenon in the Internet space. However, it is worth noting that this phenomenon first appeared not in the Internet, but in the field of sociology. The concept of "social network" as a new form of social relations has been studied by scientists since the 30s of the last century. According to the scientific definition, "social network" represents a social structure consisting of many nodes formed by social objects (people or organizations) and social relations between them [1]¹.

The fields of application of aesthetics can be classified as follows:

1) Science, field of science. Aesthetics exists as an independent discipline, but the term is also widely used in other disciplines;

¹ Umarova N. Globallashuv sharoitida axborot xurujlariga qarshi kurash. –Toshkent: Akademiya, 2005. – B. 265.

2) Field of activities. A person who is practically engaged in aesthetic activities should know the aesthetic rules, have the ability, taste, and experience them. The aesthetics of the fields of activity are divided into two:

In artistic activity, all aesthetic laws of art-related fields apply. Art, design, beauty industry, cosmetics, etc.;

In non-artistic activities - labor aesthetics, economics, marketing, medical products, etc.

3) In the sense of aesthetic value or assessment (for example, the aesthetic assessment and value of landscapes is currently determined).

4) As a factor determining the level of quality in all areas (in various business names, brands and logos).

5) In the field of education.

Literatura review.

The transformation of personal moral and aesthetic needs in cyberspace has been studied from the perspective of various social and humanitarian sciences. In his views, U. Gibson analyzed the cyberspace from the point of view of collective hallucinations, graphic representation of information from the memory banks of any computer in the human system, light lines observing the visible space of the mind [2]. Russian scientist I.A. Vasilenko tried to explain that the power and influence of any country is directly related to its place in the information space [3]. A. Muminov expressed his opinion in his monograph "Uzbekistan: Towards an Information Society" - "Users of the global network note the following inseparable advantages of information transmission among the reasons for such a wide spread of the Internet: transmission of information without printing; radio (by voice); television (audio+video)»[4]. G. Gaffarova conducted scientific research on the basis of philosophical and methodological aspects of information generation in complex systems [5]. In his studies, A. Tulyaev emphasized the importance of researching the problems of the "virtual world" in relation to sociology, cybernetics, and medicine, and daily life activities of people are actively carried out in the "virtual community", "networked society", and "cyberspace". put forward the opinion that it is increasing [6].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

Today, media products are being studied in the field of aesthetic activity. It is aesthetically interesting that many users access the Internet only to communicate through social networks. For such users, social networks are an absolute synonym of the Internet, because many things can be done through social networks: from pure communication to studying the media's agenda; examples include making purchases, watching and listening to audiovisual content. Global network users reached 4.62 billion worldwide in January 2022. This figure is equal to 58.4% of the world population. The term "social network" was first coined in 1954 by James Barnes in "Classes and Meetings in the Norwegian Island Parish". According to Barnes, "A social network consists of a social structure (mathematically - a graph), a group of nodes with social objects (people and organizations) and connections between them (social relations)." That is, at first, the appearance of the concept and its research were not related to the worldwide network. However, the rapid development of

society in the field of information technologies has already led to the development of social networks in the Internet space.

A social network is derived from the English word "social networking service" and is a network created on the basis of interactive websites with many users, whose content consists only of participants and establishes communication between them.

Regarding the use of social networks through the Internet, researcher Bitkov defines as follows: "A software service, a platform for interaction between people in a group or groups. A social network is an interactive, multi-user website whose content is populated by members of the network [7]. A website is an automated social environment that allows you to communicate with a group of users united by common interests. The basis of a social network is personal user profiles, which contain all the information related to the industry, age and other personal information that can be linked to each other.

The emergence of social networks was caused by two strong human desires. They are the need to communicate and express one's opinion. These needs have always existed and will continue to exist. Social media is a type of communication platform that is being adopted by the ever-evolving media editors today. Media events, media images, and objects of reality are critically evaluated, subjectively interpreted, and rationally explained. The most important characteristic of the communicative space is the content, in the organization of which the authors of journalistic materials and the authors of reviews act almost equally.

Social networks logically state that they have goals such as "to provide communication between people, to inform about different world news, to make friends, to help people to find their second "love", but with this they are affecting the minds of young people. It permeates popular culture and fills their minds with completely foreign romantic ideas and crude fantasies. If we look at the essence of this, we can see that someone has economic or political goals. Because after imperceptibly instilling their ideas, social networks can realize first financial, then even hidden political goals through various appeals and advertisements.

Video games in cyberspace are created in an emotional state that matches the aesthetic tastes of individuals. Along with computer graphics and web design, these games are techno-artistic twins, in which the technological basis serves not only as a means of creating an artistic product. In design, the laws of aesthetics, such as order, proportion, rhythm, harmony, symmetry, composition, texture, form and harmony of content, are applied, and it is important that the creator should have a high aesthetic taste. Modern computers are defined by their web design.

The aesthetic features of computer video games can be considered in the following.

1. The visual image of the game has a special aesthetic value - it is one of the most important elements of the commercial success of games. The visual side of games is distinguished by its own "beauty" that differs from both painting and cinematography, but at the same time, most of them (plans, compositional solutions, special effects, music), especially creating a mood through the development of emotional technologies, presents the main goal of using film media to suit human aesthetic tastes.

2. Currently, popular video games are distinguished by high-quality graphic arts that appeal to visual perception, which should create high-quality illusions. In order for the player to be in a dynamic state, he needs to experience visual pleasure through space, real-time actions, working with objects, and interacting with characters. Therefore, the general

aesthetic principle in video games is to strive for maximum realism and reliability of the image of the object, which should look realistic. With the development of virtual reality technologies, a new stage of development of electronic games and their aesthetic features took place.

3. A distinctive feature of the aesthetics of video games is the use of spatial narrative. The computer game is subject to the structure of the space in which it takes place. The plot of video games takes place with the development of the playing field. The aesthetic principle of video games is realized only when the playing field best suits the temporal aspect of the game. For example, becoming invisible through imagination. The work of the imagination is the principle from which the sensations of taste are born. Just because they come from imagination doesn't mean they're fantastic, imaginary, or ideal. They are produced worldwide by the power of imagination, which is very important because it affects the emotional functioning of the individual.

4. Games should have cultural content. The virtual world should have cultures with its own meaning and values, so historical plots, movies, and TV series often use aesthetic categories in games. The development of video games combines visual enhancement and semantic activity. When choosing games, people choose based on their attractiveness and convenience, relying on their inner feelings and usefulness.

Modern research of the aesthetic component in advertising is mainly conducted in two directions. The first includes studying the interpretation of art, its genres and styles, the use of expressive means and artistic methods to increase the attractiveness of the advertising message. The second, on the contrary, looks at advertising as a source of new directions of popular culture.

The conceptual foundations of the first approach were developed by M.M. Bakhtin said: "The three spheres of human culture - science, art and life achieve unity only in the individual, which brings them to their own unity [8]. "Esthetic activity is incapable of mastering the transitory moment and open event of existence, and its product does not exist in reality in its own sense and is attached to it in its existence through the historical action of effective aesthetic sense."

The accumulated and adapted theoretical knowledge of the artistic image, laws and genres in art, as well as the empirical experience of the use of artistic methods allowed advertising communications to form a special environment as a separate field of activity, in which the emphasis of communication finally changed. According to researchers V.Uchenova, A.Kostina, the aesthetic factor in advertising and social benefits in choosing consumer goods play a role as a catalyst and determine the trajectory of life. The general level of advertising effectiveness can reflect certain trends in culture, aesthetic taste, and demonstrate a certain level of the life of a society.

Umberto Eco considers this problem from another angle in his work "Paradoxy interpretatsii". The author identifies six interrelated and non-static functions in advertising speech, among which emotion prevails. In his opinion, the advertising message has the strongest impact on a person by appealing to human emotions, clear and hidden desires, expectations of miracles [9]. The use of various means of expression, artistic styles, gestures, styles and genres born by art allows to combine utilitarianism and aesthetics in the

advertising message, increase its effectiveness, give artistic value and thereby realize the aesthetic function of advertising communication.

CONCLUSION.

Summarizing the above approach, ideas and hypotheses, we can make the following conclusions about the importance of cyberspace tools in the transformation of aesthetic needs.

- Increasing the aesthetic culture of people in social networks through the development of personal aesthetic thinking led to the formation of today's network aesthetics;
- interest in social networks is reflected in emotions. Aesthetic feeling is the result of a person's subjective emotional attitude to the objectively expressive forms of natural and social reality, which is evaluated in accordance with the subject's perception of the social network;

- at the same time, aesthetics studies the nature of social networks, its creativity and other aspects, studies the creative essence of styles and trends in social networks;

- video games are subject to genre criteria and mass culture trends and audience interests;

- if cyberspace excites the emotions of individuals, provides harmony, beauty and attractiveness of form and content through web design, virtual games introduce them to the field of marketing through fun, usefulness, creativity, harmony and visualization, due to the development of marketing aesthetics created the aesthetics of cybermarketing, which is becoming the most profitable industry today.

- Advertising and PR create appeal with artistic forms and categories through artistic influence through broadcast images;

- social-communicative factor of marketing aesthetics - the process of product promotion in the mass media is manipulative;

- the aesthetic component of the product design (packaging, design, etc.) in the case of harmonizing the process of product development, creation and registration, defines marketing aesthetics;

the penetration of marketing into many spheres of life reflected the aesthetic worldview, the holistic view of the inner world of a person. Today, marketing aesthetics is also the main tool for implementing an effective market strategy, and it is a factor that contributes to the formation of consumer culture and the diversification of its forms.

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